

PHILOLOGY

THE USE OF CROSS-CULTURAL COMMUNICATION THEORY IN BUSINESS TRANSLATION

Aghayeva S.,

*Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University, Baku, Azerbaijan
Philology Faculty, Senior Teacher of Foreign Language Centre
ORCID: 0000-0002-5615-6923*

Huseynli A.

*Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University, Baku, Azerbaijan
Philology Faculty, Teacher of Foreign Language Centre
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4571-4678>*

Abstract

Before signing a contract or any other important document, business partners enter into communication, which can be written or oral. If we talk about forms of written communication, then, first of all, we mean business letters, which can be considered the initial stage of business relations. Oral communication includes phone calls and, of course, negotiations. Currently, almost all negotiations with foreign business partners are conducted in English, and the signing or non-signing of a contract depends on this. That is why business correspondence and negotiations must be conducted in correct and appropriate language. We have already described the most important features of business English, but we would also like to touch upon a very important and interesting problem of doing business - the cultural aspect.

Those who are engaged in business translation testify that their linguistic difficulties are as follows: special terminology, cliched vocabulary and its formal register. However, a certain linguistic literacy may prove insufficient in field conditions, when, in addition to language problems, a business translator faces completely new, but non-standard, cultural or psychological problems.

Keywords: communication, business translation, culture, language, relationships, countries.

Introduction

The need to maintain a certain "appearance" and adhere to conventions in international business communication has been recognized since the success of a company's expansion began to be measured by the number of its foreign branches or partners.

The intensification of international relations, along with obvious positive results, has led to numerous failures in negotiations, a lack of motivation among foreign interns, and even open conflicts between partners, especially those belonging to different cultures (Asian and Western, Western and Slavic). A minute-by-minute analysis of situations shows that in the impenetrable resolution of business issues, national, ethnic, psychological and cultural factors are completely ignored.

This was an impetus for methodologists and linguists to start developing a separate branch of the communication theory – Cross-Cultural Communication Studies. That encompasses ethnic culture and psychology, sociology, and a lot of other adjacent spheres. According to W. Gudykunst, W.G. Stephan, B. Blake and many other researchers of cultural diversity in the business context, communication cannot be successful unless ethno-psychological identity of its participants is recognized.

In individualistic cultures people are supposed to look after themselves and their immediate family only, while in collectivistic cultures, people belong to in-groups of collectivities which are supposed to look after them on exchange for loyalty. The example of the first culture is presented by United States, whereas Japan is an illustration of the second. This factor is to be taken into consideration in negotiations planning, since the

Japanese will never be able to take a decision which may lie beyond the interests of his corporation, and will never speak on his own behalf, whereas the individual achievements of an American may stipulate his risky decisions and possibility to take it independently. At linguistic level it stipulates the use of particular grammar structures – Active versus Passive, I / we pronouns, etc.

Communication that predominates in the cultures makes the second important criterion of cultural diversity. A high-context communication, inherent in most Asian cultures, is one in which the most information is implemented either in extra-linguistic situation of communication or is shared by the communicants, while very little is coded. A low-context communication takes place in terms of explicit code, like in Germany or the United States. This may cause the necessity to make certain aspects in business communication, e.g. price negotiations, more explicit for the Americans and less direct for the Japanese or the Chinese through the use / avoidance of certain direct grammar constructions and vocabulary. (2, 155)

Cultures with high uncertainty avoidance have a lower tolerance for uncertainty and ambiguity, which expresses itself in higher levels of anxiety and energy release, greater need for formal rules and absolute truth, and less tolerance for people in groups with deviant ideas or behavior. It was empirically confirmed that in organizations, workers in high uncertainty avoidance cultures prefer a specialist career and clear instructions, avoid conflict, and disapprove of competition between employees more than workers in low uncertainty avoidance cultures, e.g. Denmark versus Japan. It does not only stipulate the pattern of behavior with businessmen

representing these cultures but also the linguistic strategy in translation, e.g. presence or absence of mitigation markers.

Power distance is defined as the extent to which the less powerful members of institutions and organizations accept that power is distributed unequally. Individuals from high power distance cultures accept power as part of the society. Superiors there consider their subordinates to be different from themselves (Arab cultures). Low power distance cultures believe that power should be used only when it is legitimate and prefer expert or legitimate power (Western cultures). This stands for observation of subordination in the groups of businessmen, which is, for example, strict in Philippines and optional in the Netherlands. This directly influences the use of the certain vocabulary register depending on the level of communication (horizontal, with peers, or vertical, with subordinates or superiors) and the tone (type of modality, from orders to mild advice or suggestion).

The application of Cross-Cultural Communicative Theory to the business translation looks rather significant since it crucially changes the very concept of the translator's role in business communication. Supplied by the cultural knowledge, translator does not simply find equivalents of the ideas in different languages. His strategy is to maintain rapport between cultures by finding the forms of mutually accepted manner of communication, which raises his role to the global level.(1,60)

The development of business correspondence in Azerbaijan, need of official documents translation from English into Azerbaijani and vice versa after proclaiming Azerbaijani language to be state on the territory of Azerbaijan, give special significance to the language of business communication and especially to English as it is language of international communication. Business correspondence obeys certain rules of exposition and arranging of the information. Business letters have common and national specific characteristics. In all language cultures formation of official style was presupposed by the development of State system, government apparatus and by the need to confirm legal relationships

of juridical and private persons by documents. The world practice shows that despite all the peculiarities of national systems of business correspondence the main requirements to the structure, fullness of content and arrangement are stable because they had been forming historically and were determined by the peculiarities of business communication.

National specific character in business letters is performed at communicative level because peculiarities of historical development in this sphere in every nation caused the formation of specific communicational phrases and stylistic constructions. That is why while comparing standards of official style of Azerbaijani and of business correspondence, in particular with the existing standards of English business correspondence, one can distinguish ethno-linguistic characteristics of Azerbaijani and English business correspondence, which should be taken into account in translation. Azerbaijani business correspondence is characterised by the functionality (the so-called 'telegraph style'), restraint and rationality, absence of emotional colouring, estrangement of exposition is expressed through rationality and strictness of linguistic forms and patterns.

Conclusion. In comparison with Azerbaijani style, style of English business letters is characterized by more independent choice of words and syntactic constructions, by the intention of author to show his interest and willingness for close partnership with addressee, by hierarchy of polite addresses depending on the level of formal relationships between communicants.

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